

Guidelines for Optical Interfaces of Microfluidic Devices

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Introduction

Optical measurements are essential for many microfluidic devices, offering effective, quick, and reliable analysis methods on small sample volumes, for instance on a droplet of blood. In particular, microscopy is a powerful tool for monitoring and analysing cellular behaviours or fluid properties. Furthermore, microscopy is a flexible technique that can also be combined to manipulate cells or particles inside microfluidic channels using laser beams.

This document is written to serve as a guideline for researchers and engineers working in the field of microfluidics with optical interfaces. This document aims to provide direction to microfluidic engineers and scientists about what to consider when designing the device to ensure proper function of the optical parts.

As this document is created with the help of experts working on a diverse range of microfluidic products, it is expected to be applicable to a wide range of microfluidic products. The diversity in microfluidics applications and technologies is too large to create a comprehensive guideline; this document must be seen as a first step in the design process.

I. Types of optical windows and interfaces in microfluidics

There are various ways to perform optical measurements in microfluidic components. The following types of optical windows and subsequently the interfaces can be defined:

1. The **“off-chip approach”**, where a macro-scale optical infrastructure is coupled externally to a microfluidic chip, i.e., the optical system (light source, detecting system, other optical components) is not in contact with the microfluidic device. This is the preferred approach for disposable chips, just as it is for many non-microfluidic diagnostic devices.

Figure 1 (see below) illustrates the possible configurations for the light source (LS) and detecting system (D) in combination with the microfluidic device. LS and D can be positioned above and below the microfluidic chip or left and right of the chip.

Figure 1: Possible configuration of light source and detecting systems in microfluidic setup (schematic).

2. The **“on-chip approach”** integrating micro-optical functions into microfluidic devices. Prisms, lenses and various other optical components can be easily integrated into devices, for instance using 3D lithography techniques like digital light processing (DLP) or 2-photon polymerization (2PP). Furthermore, waveguides, optical gratings or fibres can also be integrated into microfluidic devices; for instance, the integration of O₂ and pH-optical fibres via Mini-Luer interfaces. For silicon devices, light source and optical detector can be integrated within the same microfluidic devices too.

This whitepaper focuses on the **“off-chip approach”** since this approach is most commonly used as of today.

II. Types of optical measurements in microfluidics

The type of measurement, but also the detection method needs to be considered when choosing the selected target to be analysed and the overall microfluidic chip design. The three most common optical methods in microfluidics are:

- Absorbance spectroscopy

The amount of light absorbed by a sample is measured at specific wavelengths. This is often used to determine the concentration of a specific substance in a microfluidic channel. A light source, a spectrometer, and a detector are required to perform this measurement.

- Fluorescence microscopy

This method is used to observe a bioprocess inside a chip (e.g., the interaction with a biomolecule with cells). The biomolecule to be observed is marked with a fluorescence marker, allowing the process to be followed by observing the inside of the chip with a microscope and recording the resulting fluorescence signals. A fluorescence microscope is required to perform this measurement, as well as a light source and an optical sensor camera to capture the images.

- Chemiluminescence microscopy

Light that emitted through a chemical reaction occurring inside a microfluidic channel is detected. With this method, one can observe and even quantify chemical reactions in microfluidics. The variety of applications ranges from immunoassays, DNA sequencing and chemical detection. Chemiluminescence requires a chemiluminescent reagents or enzymes to produce the light, a substrate for the chemiluminescent reaction to occur, a high-sensitivity camera that is sensitive enough to detect low-level light emitted by the chemiluminescent reaction and a light source to illuminate the sample.

III. Challenges in optical window design related to signal degradation.

Essential for the quality of the measurement signal is the smooth transfer of optical signal to and from the biomarker to be detected. The signal can be influenced during transfer through the optical window in the microfluidic device due to the following:

- Surface topography or roughness of the microfluidic device (channels, outside area). This can cause scattering of the light and therefore signal loss.
- Optical properties of base material (refractive index, absorbance, autofluorescence).
- Spatial/geometrical compatibility of the microfluidic setup and the optical system, for instance misalignment of parts.
- Temperature fluctuations inside the microfluidic device can cause fluctuations in the refractive index of the fluid.

When using fluorescence measurement, photo-bleaching and photo-oxidation should also be considered.

To enhance the optical properties of polymer chips and decrease reflection artefacts (for instance minimizing unwanted reflections and unspecific signals), white or black base material can be used for fluorescence or chemiluminescence measurements, respectively..

Concerning this, the thickness of the cover slides is important to consider. When using optical microscopy as the measurement method, the objective's working distance will determine the maximum cover slide thickness. Generally, the standard objectives are well suited to be used with standard cover slides (approx. 170 – 180 μm). There is a wide range of cover slides, polymer or glass, commercially available,

IV. Issues with optical windows and interfaces

Surface topography/roughness and their effects in microfluidic system

A finite composite of patches and roughness exists on almost all surfaces. In meso- and macroscale applications, rough surfaces either go unnoticed or can be ignored. With miniaturization, the surface-to-volume ratio in microfluidic devices increases rapidly, and surface properties become critical parameters for fluid behaviour, but also for the quality of the optical signal. Rough surfaces inside a channel and outside the microfluidic device can influence the optical behaviour during the measurement. For example, scattering of light can lead to errors in optical measurements.

V. Interference in optical measurement by microfluidic components

Absorbance

Usually, UV/visible absorption spectroscopy is used to measure absorbance at the macroscale level, where the attenuation of incident light is measured as a function of wavelength using a spectrophotometer. The absorption spectra peaks can characterize the sample's composition and concentration. Absorbance measurements are quantitative, as described by the Beer–Lambert law. In most bulk applications, changes in optical density or colour are sufficient. However, the optical path length through the sample on microfluidic devices decreases significantly at the microscale level, with consequences for the signal-to noise level. These affect its ability to measure low concentrations (i.e., the limit of detection).

Fluorescence

Fluorescence-based assays are widely used in microfluidic systems for molecular sensing due to their high sensitivities and specificities. Since most microfluidic devices are enclosed systems, fluorescence measurements would be affected by the optical properties and thickness of the substrate in general “off-chip” approaches. Normally, quartz and some glass substrates have very low autofluorescence. However, some polymeric materials, such as SU8, have high autofluorescence levels, which can affect the detection of low fluorescence signals. Using different excitation wavelengths can be a simple way to reduce autofluorescence, i.e., a specific excitation wavelength can selectively excite the target fluorophore while avoiding excitation of auto fluorescent materials.

Fluorescence detection can be easily implemented in portable microfluidic systems. The excitation light source can be laser diodes, which have a low divergence and can therefore easily be focused into a small detection region. As a lower-cost alternative, LEDs can be substituted for laser-based fluorescence excitation. LEDs are less ideal because of their high divergence and relatively broad emission spectra. Still, many have shown promising results with LED-induced fluorescence by incorporating integrated lenses, waveguides, and filters into their microfluidic designs. LED based fluorescence is seen as more cost effective, less harmful for the environment, and having a longer life cycle. To further increase signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), researchers have also used a synchronized dual-wavelength LED modulation approach to subtract background noise from the stray excitation light.

Refractive index

The light path changes when moving across different media. In most microfluidic devices, light travels through the air to the substrate (glass, POC, PMMA, etc.) to sample and back to the detector. When the medium changes along the light path, incident light gets diverted from the original path. This is commonly known as refraction, which is due to the change in refractive index. Overall, there is a reduction in the intensity of light passing through different media (absorbance) as well as a change in the direction of incident light (refraction). To minimize the light diverging, collimation lenses are necessary to achieve reasonable optical path lengths because light diverges from the source. Furthermore, stray light can reach the detector and reduce sensitivity.

Interface between media and their interference

The interface between materials with different optical properties is a standard method for controlling light propagation. For example, the interface between air and a dispersive material such as glass in a prism separates the colours of an incident beam into different angles. Another example can be found in fibre-optic waveguiding, in which total internal reflection at the interface between the cladding and a core with a higher refraction index confines light to the core. Therefore, for the “on-chip approach”, the interface between the optical components (such as optical fibres) can change light propagation.

In addition, small particles in a microflow, such as in colloidal optofluidic systems, can enable large changes in the optical properties of the resulting medium. For example, dielectric particles of size comparable to the wavelength can exhibit significant spectral and angular scattering variations. For example, particles that are significantly smaller than the wavelength can be used to change the medium’s refractive index or absorption coefficient. In contrast, particles that are significantly larger than the wavelength can be treated as a spherical focusing lens in the medium.

Spatial/geometrical compatibility

The spatial/geometrical compatibility of the microfluidic setup and the optical system can have significant impacts on the performance and functionality of a microfluidic system.

In general, the optical system in a microfluidic setup is used to visualize and measure various properties such as fluid flow, particle size, and cell behaviour. The optical system can include various components, such as light sources, lenses, filters, and detectors. The spatial/geometrical compatibility of the microfluidic setup and the optical system refers to how well the microfluidic device and the optical components are designed and aligned to work together seamlessly.

One important aspect of spatial/geometrical compatibility is the placement and alignment of the microfluidic device in the optical system. The device should be placed in a way that enables the optical system to view the desired region of the device with high resolution and accuracy. This can require careful alignment of the device with the optical components, as well as consideration of factors such as the refractive index of the device material.

Another important consideration is the design of the microfluidic device itself. The device should be designed to minimize optical artifacts and distortions, such as reflections, refractions, and scattering of light. This can involve optimizing the channel geometry and surface properties of the device to minimize unwanted optical effects.

Temperature fluctuations

Temperature fluctuations inside a microfluidic device can significantly impact the performance of a microfluidic optical measurement system. This is because temperature changes can affect the refractive index of the fluid inside the microfluidic channels, which can alter the path and intensity of light passing through the channels.

One way that temperature fluctuations can affect microfluidic optical measurements is by causing changes in the dimensions of the microfluidic channels. For example, if the temperature increases, the microfluidic channels may expand, leading to a decrease in the refractive index and a change in the path of light passing through the channels. This can cause errors in optical measurements, such as changes in the intensity or angle of light detected by a photodetector.

Temperature fluctuations can also cause changes in the viscosity of the fluid inside the microfluidic channels. This can lead to changes in the velocity of the fluid flow, which can in turn affect the accuracy of optical measurements of flow rates or velocities. Additionally, changes in viscosity can alter the diffusion of particles or molecules in the fluid, which can affect optical measurements of concentrations or chemical reactions.

To mitigate the impact of temperature fluctuations on microfluidic optical measurements, it is important to maintain a stable temperature inside the microfluidic device. This can be achieved by using temperature-controlled chambers or add a temperature sensor to correct the temperature impact throughout the device. Additionally, using fluids with low thermal expansion coefficients or refractive indices that are less sensitive to temperature changes can help to minimize the effects of temperature fluctuations on optical measurements.

VI. Design guidelines

To design optical interfaces for microfluidic devices, we suggest the following guidelines:

- **Type of measurement or application:** the type of measurement defines not only the setup, in which the device will be placed, but also which kind of interactions are taking place (light source, type of light, detecting signal, ...) This should be taken into account when during the design of the device.
- **Base material or choice of all materials in the device:** the properties of the material determine the outcome of the measurement. Glass and polymer based microfluidic devices can be made of various kinds of materials with varying optical properties (refractive index, absorbance, autofluorescence), which can be chosen according to the specific measurement or detection method.
- **Surface topography or roughness:** rough surfaces in channels might not only affect the flow in the device, but they can also influence the optical behaviour during the measurement. This is also valid for the device's outside surfaces to reduce losses.
- **Device geometry and setup configuration:** the device geometry should be compatible with the setup from which the measurement will be conducted. The optical window of the device should fit the area for inspection, but it should also give enough space for the light source and detection system. Preferred cover slides range from 120 to 200 μ m to match standards used in microscopy.
- **Optimize the detection system by considering the signal-to-noise ratio, the sensitivity of the detector and temperature effect.** This may involve optimizing the light intensity, the wavelength range, and the detector size and sensitivity.
- **Test and validate the optical interface by performing experiments to verify the accuracy and precision of the optical measurements or analyses.** This may involve using standards or known samples to validate the measurement or analysis results.

Recommended further reading.

This whitepaper only gives a general overview of the problems encountered when designing an optical microfluidic system. More detailed information can be found in one of the following articles:

General reading

Zhou, Pan, et al. "A review of optical imaging technologies for microfluidics." *Micromachines* 13.2 (2022): 274.

Specific articles

Eliminating air bubbles in microfluidic systems:

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10544-020-00529-w>

Raman spectroscopy:

<https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/23/2/781>

On-chip fluorescence detection:

<https://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/5.0102071>